

Aldehydofluorescein and Dyes Derived from it.

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By the application of Reimer-Tiemann's reaction it has been found that the aldehyde group may be introduced into coumarin (Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2428) or phenolphthalein (Sen and Kar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 54). Fluorescein also being subjected to the same reaction gives an aldehyde (I).

The aldehyde group may take any of the positions marked with asterisks, preferably a position *para* to the pyronine oxygen atom and *ortho* to any of the hydroxyl groups. The strength of the alkali to be used and the time and temperature of the reaction are of great importance to get a good yield of the aldehyde. After careful investigation, it has been observed that about 50% caustic soda solution and the temperature of the boiling water-bath for 15 to 20 hours give the best yield, which is about 45% of the theoretical. If alkali of lesser strength and lower temperature be used much unaltered fluorescein is left behind. The purification may be best effected through the bisulphite compound of the aldehyde as described in the experimental portion. It is really interesting to note that with the introduction of the aldehyde group in fluorescein, the fluorescence is diminished to a considerable extent. This diminution of fluorescent property may be ascribed to the fact that with

the introduction of the aldehyde group, the symmetry of the molecule is affected (Hewitt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1251). The aldehyde also differs from fluorescein in many other respects. Its solubility in absolute alcohol is much greater than that of fluorescein itself. In finely powdered state fluorescein exhibits a brick-red colour but the aldehyde in the same condition is yellowish brown. Whereas fluorescein gives a yellow solution with intense green fluorescence in alcohol, the aldehyde gives a deep red solution with much subdued green fluorescence in the same solvent. While fluorescein dyes wool and silk bright yellow shades, the aldehyde dyes wool and silk deep orange shades, the deeper colour being evidently due to the aldehyde group which acts as an additional chromophore. Fluorescein as well as the aldehyde are insoluble in water and also in ether, chloroform, benzene, etc., and both of them are soluble in alkali and also in alcohol and acetone.

The aldehyde gives a hydrazone (II), a semicarbazone (III), and a dioxime (IV).

It is noticed that the strong fluorescent property of fluorescein already diminished to a great extent by the advent of the aldehyde group disappears completely in hydrazone, semicarbazone and oxime. It appears that this may be due partly to the unsymmetry of the molecules and partly to the introduction of the nitrogen element in the molecules. It will be observed later on that with the introduction of the nitrogen atom in the molecule the fluorescent property generally disappears. The hydrazone, semicarbazone and dioxime all dye silk and wool dull pink shades.

The dioxime-formation is confirmed by the observation now made for the first time that fluorescein itself gives a monoxime (V) when treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride under similar conditions (*cf.* phenolphthaleinoxime, *Ber.*, 1893, 26, 172; *ibid.*, 1895, 28, 3258; Orndorff and Murray, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 19 7, 39, 679).

Fluorescein itself is insoluble in ether, whereas its oxime is fairly soluble. It is very remarkable that the fluorescent property is not so markedly affected as in the case of the aldehyde and its hydrate and oxime derivatives.

The aldehyde also gives a bisulphite compound which is very readily soluble in water and is not at all fluorescent even in alkaline solution.

Several interesting dyes with multiple chromophores have been derived from aldehydofluorescein. Thus (i) azomethine dyes have been obtained by condensing the aldehyde with monoamines, diamines and certain dyes containing free NH_2 groups; (ii) triphenylmethane dyes have been obtained by condensing the aldehyde with dimethylaniline and *o*-cresotinic acid; (iii) pyronine dyes have also been obtained by the condensation of the aldehyde with resorcinol and dimethyl-*m*-aminophenol.

To get azomethine dyes condensations have been effected in absolute alcoholic medium on the boiling water-bath. It is noted in this connection that alkaline solutions of these compounds do not exhibit any fluorescence. This is perhaps due to the entrance of the nitrogen element in the molecule. These compounds are generally coloured, micro-crystalline substances dyeing silk and wool with shades varying from yellow to reddish brown.

In cases of monoamines such as aminoazobenzene (VI), *p*-toluidine (VII) and *p*-nitraniline (VIII), only one molecule of the aldehyde reacts with one molecule of each of them.

While the diamines such as benzidine (IX), *o*-phenylenediamine (X) and *p*-phenylenediamine (XI) react with two molecules of the aldehyde. *o*-Phenylenediamine and benzidine compounds dye silk and wool yellowish pink shades but the compound from *p*-phenylenediamine dyes silk and wool brown shades. All of them fail to exhibit any fluorescence in any solvent.

With *m*-phenylenediamine (XII), rosaniline (XIII) and chrysoidine (XIV) however, only one molecule of the aldehyde reacts, the presence of free amino-group being indicated by the evolution of nitrogen when heated with nitrous acid and also by the diazo-reaction and formation of azo-compounds. None of the products of these condensations exhibit any fluorescence in any solvent. Further, the intensity of colour of rosaniline and chrysoidine is also very much diminished by condensation with the aldehyde owing perhaps to the elimination of the auxochromic effect of one of the NH_2 groups.

By the condensation of aldehydofluorescein with dimethylaniline, a leuco-base (XV) is obtained in colourless needle-shaped crystals which gradually turn bluish due to atmospheric oxidation, and gives

a beautiful blue basic dye when oxidized with lead peroxide in the usual manner. Unlike fluorescein and the aldehydofluorescein, the leuco-base is very readily soluble in cold chloroform giving a bluish-violet solution. It also differs from the aldehyde very markedly in other respects, *e.g.*, it is readily soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid giving a bluish-green solution and it is soluble in alcohol giving a violet solution but it is not soluble in caustic alkalis. In this case also it is noticed that the fluorescent property altogether disappears. Two molecules of dimethylaniline react with one molecule of the aldehyde. The hydrochloride (XVI) of the product derived from the leuco-base, on oxidation with lead peroxide in the usual manner, dyes wool and silk beautiful deep blue shades.

By the condensation of aldehydofluorescein with *o*-cresotinic acid in presence of sulphuric acid (*d* 1'84) in the cold, another triphenylmethane dye (XVII) has been obtained. The leuco-compound dyes silk and wool an orange-yellow shade which is deeper (*i.e.*, redder) than that of fluorescein itself and lighter (*i.e.*, more yellow) than that of the aldehyde. It is interesting to note that the compound exhibits fluorescence in alcoholic and alkaline solutions, which is more marked than that of aldehydofluorescein. Oxidation of the leuco-compound with nitrosyl sulphate gives a dark red compound which dyes silk and wool deep brown shades.

With dimethyl-*m*-aminophenol in the presence of sulphuric acid (*d* 1'84) at 160-170°, aldehydofluorescein gives a fine reddish-violet dye (XVIII) analogous to the rhodamines. Sulphuric acid in this case acts both as a condensing and an oxidizing agent, as is evidenced

by the copious evolution of sulphur dioxide during the course of the reaction.

It is to be noted however that below 140° there is practically no evolution of sulphur dioxide. Analytical results show that four molecules of dimethyl-*m*-aminophenol react with one molecule of aldehydofluorescein, both the CH:O and C:O groups taking part in the reaction. Sen and Guha-Sarkar studied the reactivity of the C:O group in the lactone ring (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 150) and as further corroboration it is now found that fluorescein itself also condenses with two molecules of dimethyl-*m*-aminophenol in the presence of sulphuric acid ($d\ 1.84$) at $150\text{--}160^\circ$ to give a compound (XIX) of the type of rhodamine which dyes silk and wool bluish-pink shades while the compound (XVIII) with the aldehyde dyes silk and wool a bluish violet shade. It is interesting to note that both the compounds are strongly fluorescent in alcoholic and alkaline solutions. This may perhaps be due to the introduction of additional pyronine rings. Both the compounds are soluble in acid and alkali.

Aldehydofluorescein has also been condensed with resorcinol (XX) in presence of sulphuric acid (d 1.84) at 100° for 3 to 4 hours in the manner described by Sen and Sinha (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2984). Here two molecules of resorcinol react with one molecule of aldehydofluorescein giving a brownish red compound which dyes silk and wool red-orange shades. On brominating the compound, a deep red pentabromo-derivative is obtained which dyes silk and wool dark red shades. The compound with resorcinol is more strongly fluorescent than the aldehyde and this may be ascribed also to the introduction of the additional pyronine ring.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of Aldehydofluorescein (I).—The crude aldehyde, prepared by the method applied in the case of aldehydophenolphthalein (Sen and Kar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 56) is extracted with cold absolute alcohol, the alcoholic extract poured into acidified water with constant stirring, the precipitate filtered, washed with warm water and finally crystallised from dilute alcohol. Yield 45%.

It may be obtained in an extra pure condition by decomposing, with hot dilute hydrochloric acid, the bisulphite compound of the aldehyde prepared by shaking, for a long time, a saturated aqueous solution of sodium bisulphite with the solid aldehyde which ultimately goes into solution. The bisulphite compound may also be obtained in light orange-yellow crystalline form by adding a saturated aqueous solution of sodium bisulphite to an absolute alcoholic solution of the aldehyde and keeping the mixture overnight. It is extremely soluble in cold water giving a light orange solution, and in alkali giving a deep red solution. It is insoluble in alcohol, chloroform, ether but soluble in acetone. It does not exhibit any fluorescence.

The aldehyde is a yellowish-brown micro-crystalline solid readily soluble in alkali, giving a dark red solution with green fluorescence. It is also soluble in alcohol, acetone, glacial acetic acid, nitrobenzene, but practically insoluble in ether, chloroform and benzene. It dyes wool and silk a bright orange shade. It does not melt up to 260° . (Found: C, 69.8; H, 3.7. $C_{21}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 70.0; H, 3.3 per cent.)

Derivatives of Aldehydofluorescein.—The *phenylhydrazone* (II) was prepared by heating a mixture of the aldehyde and phenylhydrazine

in absolute alcohol on a water-bath for 2 to 3 hours ; on cooling, the hydrazone separated out. It was filtered, washed with acidified water and finally crystallised from dilute alcohol. It is a micro-crystalline powder, soluble in alcohol and acetone, and also in alkali with a deep red solution but no fluorescence. It does not melt up to 260°. (Found: N, 6·57. $C_{27}H_{18}O_5N_2$ requires N, 6·22 per cent.)

The *semicarbazone* (III) was prepared in the usual manner, and was crystallised from dilute alcohol ; a reddish-brown micro-crystalline substance, soluble in alkali, alcohol and acetone and insoluble in chloroform and ether was obtained. It does not melt up to 260°. (Found: N, 10·6. $C_{22}H_{15}O_6N_3$ requires N, 10·07 per cent.)

The *dioxime* (IV) was prepared as the dioxime of phenolphthalein-aldehyde (Sen and Kar, *loc. cit.*). The product when washed with acetone formed a dark red micro-crystalline powder, soluble in boiling water, alkali, dilute alcohol, and insoluble in chloroform, acetone, benzene and ether ; it does not melt up to 260°. (Found: N, 7·38. $C_{22}H_{14}O_6N_2$ requires N, 6·96 per cent.)

Fluorescein-monoxime (V).—Prepared and purified as the above dioxime ; it was finally extracted with ether. An orange-yellow micro-crystalline solid, soluble in alkali and alcohol with green fluorescence. It does not melt up to 260°. (Found: N, 3·6. $C_{20}H_{13}O_5N$ requires N, 3·7 per cent.)

Azomethine Dyes.

Fluoresceinal-aminoazobenzene (VI).—It was prepared as phenolphthaleinal-*p*-toluidine (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 57), the heating being continued for 3-4 hours. The product is filtered, the residue washed with water acidified with hydrochloric acid, and finally with warm alcohol; crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and glacial acetic acid (4: 1) as a reddish-brown micro-crystalline solid, soluble readily in glacial acetic acid and sparingly in alcohol and acetone. It does not melt up to 260°. It is not fluorescent, dyes yellow shade on wool and silk. Yield almost theoretical. (Found: N, 7·39. $C_{34}H_{21}O_5N_3$ requires N, 7·62 per cent.)

Other azomethine dyes are listed in the annexed table.

Triphenylmethane Dyes.

Tetramethyldiaminodiphenylfluorescein-methane (XV), prepared as the analogous compound of aldehydophenolphthalein (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 58), crystallised from chloroform as light blue

small needles melting at 70°-72°. It is very readily soluble in chloroform, alcohol and ether giving reddish-violet solutions with no fluorescence. The acid solution is light bluish-green. Yield, 80 per cent. (Found: N, 5·05. $C_{38}H_{32}O_5N_2$ requires N, 4·79 per cent.).

The oxidation of the above leuco-base is carried out in the usual manner with freshly precipitated lead peroxide; a bluish substance was obtained. The hydrochloride of this dyes a deep blue shade on wool and silk.

Dimethyldihydroxydicarboxydiphenylfluorescein-methane (XVII).—It was prepared as the analogous compound of aldehydophenolphthalein (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 58). The product was washed with chloroform and crystallised from dilute alcohol as a micro-crystalline yellow substance, sparingly soluble in warm water, readily soluble in alcohol and acetone. Alkaline and alcoholic solutions exhibit red-green fluorescence; it does not melt up to 260°. Light orange-yellow shade on silk and wool (yield, 80 per cent.). (Found: C, 68·2; H, 4·1. $C_{37}H_{26}O_{11}$ requires C, 68·7; H, 4·02 per cent.).

The above leuco-base is oxidised with nitrosyl sulphate at 50°-60° when a dark red powder soluble in alcohol and acetone is obtained. It dyes silk and wool a deep brown shade.

Pyronine Dyes.

Fluoresceinal-rhodamine (XVIII).—A mixture of dried aldehydofluorescein (2 g.), dried dimethyl-*m*-aminophenol (3 g.) and sulphuric acid (5 c.c., *d* 1·84) is heated on the oil-bath at 150°-160° for 4 to 5 hours with an air condenser. During the course of heating, sulphur dioxide is evolved as is evidenced by its odour and by the development of a blue colour on starch iodate paper. The molten mass is then cooled and treated with water, filtered and thoroughly washed with water. It is then dissolved in warm dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitated by ammonia. The solution and precipitation are repeated, and the washed residue is finally purified from alcohol and carbon bisulphide and obtained in the form of a pink powder. Yield, 70 per cent.

It dissolves in acid and alkalis with green-red fluorescence which is more marked in organic solvents; it dyes wool and silk a fine bluish-violet shade. It does not melt up to 260°. (Found: N, 7·06. $C_{53}H_{48}O_7N_4$ requires N, 6·7 per cent.). Fluorescein itself condenses with dimethyl-*m*-aminophenol under similar conditions as above

and gives a reddish-pink substance, soluble in acids and alkalis and also in alcohol and acetone with marked green fluorescence. It dyes wool and silk a bluish pink shade. It softens at 245°. (Found N, 4.96. $C_{36}H_{30}O_5N_2$ requires N, 4.91 per cent.).

Diresorcinol-fluorescein.— A mixture of aldehydofluorescein (2 g.), dried resorcinol (4 g.) and sulphuric acid (3 c.c., *d* 1.84) is heated on the boiling water-bath for 2 hours with an air condenser. Copious evolution of sulphur dioxide takes place. The melt, when cooled, is treated with ice-cold water, filtered and thoroughly washed with cold water. The residue is dissolved in caustic soda solution, and the compound is precipitated with dilute hydrochloric acid: the solution and precipitation are repeated several times. The product is then dissolved in alcohol and boiled with animal charcoal several times. The cooled filtrate is poured into water till a turbidity is produced. It is then filtered and the filtrate allowed to stand overnight with more water. The precipitate, thus obtained, is filtered and dried on a porous plate and finally in a desiccator (yield, 40 per cent.).

It is a dark red powder, sparingly soluble in cold water, easily soluble in alcohol and acetone, and insoluble in chloroform and ether. It imparts a red-green fluorescence, more intense than that of aldehydofluorescein, to alkaline and alcoholic solutions; it dyes wool and silk a red-orange shade; it does not melt up to 260°. (Found: C, 72.2; H, 3.75. $C_{33}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 73.06; H, 3.3 per cent.).

The *pentabromo*-derivative was prepared and purified in the usual way. It is a deep red substance, insoluble in water, readily soluble in alkali and alcohol. It does not exhibit any fluorescence. It produces a deep red shade on silk and wool. (Found: Br, 42.01. $C_{33}H_{13}O_8Br_5$ requires Br, 42.6 per cent.).

Azomethine Dyes.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation.	M.P. and appearance.	P.c. of N (calc. values in brackets).	Properties.
Fluorescein- <i>p</i> -toluidine.	VII.	Aldehydofluorescein + <i>p</i> -toluidine (in alcohol) on water-bath for 3-4 hours. Yield, 90%.	Does not melt up to 260°. Reddish-brown powder.	3.05% (3.11)	Soluble in alkali giving red solution; sparingly soluble in alcohol; no fluorescence. Light yellow-orange shade on wool and silk.
- <i>p</i> -nitraniline.	VIII.	Aldehydofluorescein + <i>p</i> -nitraniline (in alcohol) on water-bath for 3-4 hours.	Does not melt up to 260°. Yellow powder.	5.6% (5.69)	Sparingly soluble in alcohol, insoluble in water and ether. Yellow shade on wool and silk.
-benzidine.	IX.	Aldehydofluorescein + benzidine (in alcohol) on water-bath for 3-4 hours. Yield, theoretical.	Does not melt up to 260°. Reddish-brown micro-crystalline powder.	3.37% (3.22)	Soluble in alkali giving a deep red solution, insoluble in water, boiling alcohol, chloroform and ether. No fluorescence.
- <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine.	X.	Aldehydofluorescein + <i>o</i> -phenylenediamine (in alcohol) on water-bath for 3-4 hours. Yield, 60%.	Does not melt up to 250°. Yellow powder.	3.63% (3.53)	No fluorescence. Sparingly soluble in alcohol and acetone, insoluble in water, ether and chloroform. Orange-yellow shade on wool and silk.
- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine.	XI.	Aldehydofluorescein + <i>p</i> -phenylenediamine (in alcohol) on water-bath for 3-4 hours. Yield 40%.	Does not melt up to 260°. Yellowish-brown powder.	3.3% (3.53)	Very sparingly soluble in absolute alcohol; insoluble in water, ether and chloroform. No fluorescence. Brown shade on wool and silk.

Name.	Formula.	Method of preparation.	M.P. and appearance.	P. c. of N (calc. values in brackets).	Properties.
<i>m</i> -phenylenediamine.	XII.	Aldehydofluorescein + <i>m</i> -phenylene-diamine (in alcohol) on water-bath for 3-4 hours. Yield, theoretical.	Does not melt up to 260°. Brown micro-crystalline powder.	6.23% (6.22)	Very sparingly soluble in cold alcohol, insoluble in water, ether and chloroform. Reddish-yellow shade on wool and silk.
Fluoresceinal-rosaniline.	XIII.	Aldehydofluorescein + rosaniline (in alcohol) on water-bath for 3-4 hours. Yield, theoretical.	Does not melt up to 260°. Reddish-violet powder.	6.9% (6.85)	Soluble in alkali giving a deep red solution with no fluorescence; sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone and nitrobenzene; insoluble in water, ether, benzene and carbon tetrachloride. Pink shade on wool and silk.

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